

Interactions in mathematics classrooms over different timescales

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I here introduce a classroom study that takes a dialogical approach on mathematics teaching and learning to investigate in what ways interactions between the participants in the classroom are interconnected over different timescales when communicating mathematical reasoning. The study is part of my ongoing PhD-work with an aim to further understand the connections between in the moment interactions and longer patterns of interactions in mathematics classrooms in upper secondary school in Norway.

Context

To understand teaching, we need to think about how students take part in activities in the classroom and in education research look at what learning opportunities students are given and what systems they are part of (Staples, 2008). Franke, Kazemi and Battey (2007) show how teachers' choices of actions and activities in teaching influence the conditions for interactions in the classroom, creating different opportunities for students to engage with mathematics and with other students. Equally, students' reactions or expectations and attitudes towards mathematics influence interactions, how they engage and what meaning knowledge is given. In this flow of interactions between participants in the classroom there is also a negotiation for what is allowed or expected to be done in the mathematics classroom (Cobb, 1999). Depending on responses from students, the teacher makes new choices that have impact not only in the moment (Bishop, 2008) but affect what happens in the next lesson or several lessons to come, creating an ongoing change in conditions for teaching and learning.

Curriculum documents in Europe highlight developing a mathematical competence (OECD, 2018) as a central goal for teaching mathematics, but the translation of such competence differ between education systems and are hence used in different ways in research depending on the context. In the ongoing renewal of the curriculum in Norway (Kunnskapsdepartementet, 2020), the concept of competence is described in terms of basic communication skills (to speak, to read, to write, to count and digital skills) and core elements, such as reasoning and argumentation, that teaching should address in all school subjects and on all educational levels. In mathematics, such competence involves students' ability using mathematical concepts in different situations, their capability of engaging in posing and answering questions related to mathematics and their use of mathematical

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language. Such aspects of students becoming active members of the mathematical discourse in the classroom are also present in education research, for example how participating in conversations about mathematics promotes students understanding of mathematical concepts or development of a formal mathematical language (Schleppegrell, 2007; Barwell, 2016).

Changes in learning conditions influencing teaching in longer timescales than a lesson implies that research on teaching needs to include studies that tie together how students approach or understand mathematical content during parts of individual lessons with how a teacher organizes the classroom also for longer learning processes (Klette, 2007). Although there are several studies in education research that address how time can alter ones understanding of mathematics, there have been more studies on shorter social processes such as those taking place during classroom lessons than on processes that lasts days or weeks (Lemke, 2000). To look at a sequence of lessons in different timescales could affect how classroom activities and interactions are analysed and classified in research (Dalland et al., 2020) and to investigate connections between interactions from different parts of such a sequence could give a new contribution to the understanding of teaching and learning mathematics.

Purpose and aim

The project I present here is part of my ongoing PhD-work with a research interest in the interactions that take place in the classrooms of novice teachers when communicating mathematical reasoning. The study is to be conducted in upper secondary school in Norway and a novice teacher has in this context up to three years of experience teaching mathematics since graduating from teacher education. Three questions guide my research: 1) What kind of patterns of interactions are established in the classroom when the new teacher and students are communicating mathematical reasoning? 2) What are the relationships between the mathematical content and patterns of interactions in the classroom? 3) How do patterns in classroom interactions connect to, or influence each other, over different timescales?

Focus for this project presentation is the third research question, with the aim to further understand how individual events in the mathematics classroom can be interconnected with longer teaching and learning processes when looking at more than just a single lesson. My study proposes to examine the shifts in learning conditions and students' opportunities to participate in the classroom by following interactions over a sequence of lessons. I use 'patterns in classroom interactions' to address "identifiable types of exchanges" (Lemke, 2000, p. 276) that evolve or reoccur over time.

Theoretical aspects of the research

With an interest in classroom interactions and communication I choose a theoretical starting point looking at learning and teaching as social practice and that humans are interdependent of others (Linell, 2009). The meaning of actions and knowledge are created together by the

participants in a context that also influence the communication and negotiation of that meaning. In mathematics such meaning-making could be about a mathematical concept or to understand what counts as an acceptable mathematical explanation and justification in the classroom (Cobb, 1999).

One theoretical framework that highlights interactions, language and the influence of contexts is dialogism (Linell, 2009). In dialogism meaning-making is described as being multi-voiced and interactive and a dialogical research approach puts all the participants in the mathematics classroom as contributors to the dialogues and the meaning of mathematics (Barwell, 2016). Using the theoretical framework of dialogism as presented by Linell (2009) enables dialogues to be about all kind of human sense making and enables patterns in classroom discussions to be about social actions where participants interact with others depending on the situated linguistic practice. Participating in communication can then be a sign of learning and this classroom study seeks to develop understanding for what this participation looks like rather than for how or why interactions take place.

To address how interactions can be connected over time I will use the concept of different timescales presented by Lemke (2000). Timescales are then divided by powers of ten, for example utterance and the exchange of them being at the scale $1-10^2$ seconds and a school day and units of them at the scale 10^5-10^6 seconds. According to Lemke it is especially interactions in the scale directly under and over the one in focus of an observation that is of interest to study. Lemke also uses semiotic artifacts to visualise how interactions on different timescales are connected in time and space through physical objects or utterances that reoccur in different situations. To follow dialogues over time, in a fairly limited context, could enable findings of interaction that form patterns both in language and other interactions with the environment that are not just accidental expressions and acts of routine but are bearing some kind of meaning or reason (Linell, 2009).

Methodology

To address my research question about how events and interactions in mathematics classroom can be connected over time I plan to do classroom observations and visit three to four classrooms, and by that three to four different teachers. Observations and recorded video data from a sequence of lessons would enable studies of dialogues at micro and macro levels (Lemke, 2000) and by that identify interactions on different timescales. I intend to use Lemke's timescale of 10-12 days as a unit for the sequence of mathematics lessons to follow and then look at interactions within lessons, between lessons and over the entire period's timescale. Recordings make it possible to capture actions and things that can be analysed to connect different timescales, for example gestures, use of physical objects in different ways or words or utterances that reoccur over time. Patterns in interactions could also be connected to the level of responses given by students, the use of activities or the use of time and space in the classroom. Analysis of video recordings would make it possible to find thematic patterns in interactions, although there are challenges in finding those patterns and connecting interactions to a relevant timescale.

Challenges and final remarks

To conclude, previous research results have put into focus the importance of more detailed studies of how interactions affect the conditions for teaching and learning and I find the aspects of meaning-making, dialogues and timescales being highly relevant to further understand mathematics teaching and interactions in the classroom. Although video recordings make it possible to capture different interactions, finding those patterns in the recorded data pose a challenge not only in relation to the amount of data but in finding timescales and identifying relevant artifacts and aspects of dialogues to follow. I find this conference to be a good opportunity to meet with other colleagues of the community and discuss this study, its possibilities, and challenges.

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